

MUHANDISLIK

& IQTISODIYOT

*ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal*

2026-YIL
IYUN/6-SON, III-QISM

Milliy nashrlar

OAK: <https://oak.uz/pages/4802>

05.00.00 – Texnika fanlari

08.00.00 – Iqtisodiyot fanlar

Google Scholar

ISSN INTERNATIONAL STANDARD SERIAL NUMBER INTERNATIONAL CENTRE

OpenAIRE

ISSN: 3060-463X

muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Elektron nashr, 2026-yil, iyun.

Bosh muharrir:

Zokirova Nodira Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, DSc, professor

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Shakarov Zafar G'afarovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, PhD, dotsent

Tahrir hay'ati:

Abduraxmanov Kalendar Xodjayevich, O'z FA akademigi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Maxkamov Baxtiyor Shuxratovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shaumarov Said Sanatovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Turayev Bahodir Xatamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Nasimov Dilmurod Abdulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Allayeva Gulchexra Jalgasovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Arabov Nurali Uralovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Maxmudov Odiljon Xolmirzayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Xamrayeva Sayyora Nasimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bobonazarova Jamila Xolmurodovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Irmatova Aziza Baxromovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bo'taboyev Mahammadjon To'ychiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shamshiyeva Nargizaxon Nosirxuja kizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor,

Xolmuxamedov Muhsinjon Murodullayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Xodjayeva Nodiraxon Abdurashidovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Amanov Otabek Amankulovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Qurbonov Samandar Pulatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Zikriyoyev Aziz Sadulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Tabayev Azamat Zaripbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sxay Lana Aleksandrovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Ismoilova Gulnora Fayzullayevna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Djumaniyazov Umrbek Ilxamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kasimova Nargiza Sabitdjanovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kalanova Moxigul Baxritdinovna, dotsent

Ashurzoda Luiza Muxtarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sharipov Sardor Begmaxmat o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Tursunov Ulug'bek Sativoldiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Bauyetdinov Majit Janizaqovich, Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti dotsenti, PhD

Botirov Bozorbek Musurmon o'g'li, Texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sultonov Shavkatjon Abdullayevich, Kimyo fanlari doktori, (DSc)

Jo'raeva Malohat Muhammadovna, filologiya fanlari doktori (DSc), professor.

Yusupov Maxamadamin Abduxamidovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (DSc), professor

Kalonova Moxigul Baxritdinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent

Mirzayev Kulmamat Djanzakovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (DSc), professor.

Karimova Nilufar Sadirdin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Norboyev Odil Abrayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Nasimov Dilmurod Abdulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Mirzayev Kulmamat Djanzakovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Karimova Nilufar Sadirdin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Pardaev Umidjon Uralovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Xolmirzayev Ulug'bek Abdulazizovich, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc)

muhandislik & iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
05.08.06 – "G'ildirakli va gusenisali mashinalar va ularni ishlatish" (texnika fanlari)
05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari
10.00.06 – Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik, chog'ishtirma tilshunoslik va tarjimashunoslik
10.00.04 – Yevropa, Amerika va Avstraliya xalqlari tili va adabiyoti
08.00.01 – Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
08.00.02 – Makroiqtisodiyot
08.00.03 – Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
08.00.04 – Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
08.00.05 – Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
08.00.06 – Ekonometrika va statistika
08.00.07 – Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
08.00.08 – Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
08.00.09 – Jahon iqtisodiyoti
08.00.10 – Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
08.00.11 – Marketing
08.00.12 – Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
08.00.13 – Menejment
08.00.14 – Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
08.00.15 – Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Ma'lumot uchun, OAK
Rayosatining 2024-yil 28-avgustdagi 360/5-son qarori bilan "Dissertatsiyalar asosiy ilmiy natijalarini chop etishga tavsiya etilgan milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxati"ga texnika va iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali ro'yxatga kiritilgan.

Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz:

1. Toshkent shahridagi G.V.Plexanov nomidagi Rossiya iqtisodiyot universiteti
2. Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti
3. Toshkent irrigatsiya va qishloq xo'jaligini mexanizatsiyalash muhandislari instituti" milliy tadqiqot universiteti
4. Islom Karimov nomidagi Toshkent davlat texnika universiteti
5. Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti
6. Toshkent davlat transport universiteti
7. Toshkent arxitektura-qurilish universiteti
8. Toshkent kimyo-texnologiya universiteti
9. Jizzax politexnika instituti

MUNDARIJA

RIVOJLANAYOTGAN MAMLAKATLARDA ESG TAMOYILLARINI JORIY ETISHNING INSTITUTSIONAL TO'SIQLARI VA IQTISODIY OQIBATLARI	10
I. R. Berdikulova	
KIMYO SANOATINING IQTISODIYOTDA TUTGAN O'RNI VA TARMOQ KORXONALARIDA BOSHQARUV HISOBI	14
Onorboev Sh.M.	
A WEEKLY LOGISTICS-CONTROLLING SYSTEM FOR EXPORT SUPPLY CHAINS: CORRIDOR-LEVEL EVIDENCE FROM A TEXTILE EXPORTER.....	26
Mukhammadiyahaminova Shakhzoda Sherzodovna	
FOTOVOLTAIK-TROMBE DEVORI ASOSIDA HAVONI ISITISH, TOZALASH VA ELEKTR ENERGIYASI ISHLAB CHIQRISH JARAYONLARINI INTEGRATSIYALASHNING ILMIY-METODIK TAHLILI.....	36
Rahimova Volida Karim qizi	
XAVFSIZ HAYOT TARZINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA TA'LIM VA TARBIYANING O'RNI: NAZARIY ASOSLAR VA AMALIY MODEL.....	42
Nigmatjonov Sardor Abdumannovich	
РАЗВИТИЕ МЕТОДОЛОГИИ ВНЕДРЕНИЯ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ СТРАТЕГИЙ НА ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ ПИЩЕВОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ: КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНЫЙ ПОДХОД.....	49
Дониёрова Зухрабону Алишер кизи	
KAMBAG'AL OILALARNI TADBIRKORLIKKA JALB QILISHDA DAVLAT TOMONIDAN MOLIVAVIY QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH VA BOSHQARISH (MENEJMENT) TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI...53	
Bazarbaeva Asiya Shalkarbaevna	
MOLIVAVIY INKLYUZIVLIK KONSEPSIYASI: BANK XIZMATLARINING KAMBAG'ALLIK DARAJASIGA TA'SIRINING NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA O'ZBEKISTON AMALIYOTI.....	58
Niyozov Zuxur, Abdujalilov Shexroz, Zubaydulloyeva Damira	
KORXONALARNI QAYTA TASHKIL ETISH JARAYONIDA ASOSIY VOSITALAR HISOBI VA BAHOLASHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	61
Davletov Ikrom Raximberganovich	
ИОРДАНИЯ КАК ТУРИСТИЧЕСКИЙ ЦЕНТР БЛИЖНЕГО ВОСТОКА.....	67
Салихова Алина Муратовна	
QUYOSH ENERGIYASINI KONVERSIYALOVCHI OPTOELEKTRON GELIOTRANSFORMATORLARNING FIZIK-TEXNIK ASOSLARI	73
Axunov Qambarali, Xomidov Abdullajon, Mashrapova Irodaxon	
XXI ASRDA O'ZBEKISTONDA ELEKTR ENERGIYASINI TEJASHDAGI YANGI TEXNOLOGIYALAR.....	78
Xamrakulova Xilola, Yusupova Sevaraxon	
HUDUDIY IXTISOSLASHUVNING SHAKLLANISH OMILLARI VA MINTAQAVIY RIVOJLANISHDAGI AHAMIYATI	83
Sodiqova Nigora	
BANKLAR TRANSFORMATSIYASI JARAYONIDA AKTIVLAR SAMARADORLIGI TAHLILI.....	89
Muminov Bekzod Polvonovich	
ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКИЙ КАПИТАЛ КАК КЛЮЧЕВОЙ ФАКТОР УСТОЙЧИВОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	95
Садыков Авазбек Мадаминович, Цхай Лана Александровна	
MILLIY KADRLAR ZAXIRASINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING ILG'OR XORIJ TAJRIBASI.....	103
G'aniyev Elyor Sobirjonovich	
DIGITALIZATION OF INSOLVENCY PROCESSES: THE ROLE OF A UNIFIED ELECTRONIC PLATFORM IN ENSURING TRANSPARENCY AND ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY	110
Damirjon Nurmatovich Soliyev	

О ПРОЦЕССАХ ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	116
Джумаев Аскар Хайдарович	
SOLIQ MA'MURCHILIGI METODOLOGIYASINING HUQUQIY, TASHKILY VA RAQAMLI BAZASINI SHAKLLANTIRISH BILAN BOG'LIQ MUAMMOLAR.....	121
Shamsiev O'ktam Sayfitdinovich	
KO'P XONADONLI UYLARDA KOMMUNAL XIZMATLAR KO'RSATISH SOHASINING INSTITUTSIONAL ASOSLARI VA HOZIRGI HOLATI TAHLILI.....	127
Muminov Obidjon Odilovich	
MINTAQA VA UNING HUDUDLARIDA MEHNAT OMILI HISOBIGA SANOAT SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	135
Urazaliyev Bekzod Sultanbayevich	
КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯ ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ ПРИНЯТИЯ РЕШЕНИЙ С УЧЕТОМ ОПТИМИЗАЦИИ БИЗНЕС ПРОЦЕССОВ.....	141
Джуманов А.А.	
O'ZBEKISTONDA SOLIQ MADANIYATINI SHAKLLANTIRUVCHI OMILLARNI FAKTOR TAHLIL VA KO'P OMILLI REGRESSIYA ASOSIDA BAHOLASH.....	152
V.I. Isroilov, V.B. Ibragimov	
ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА В РАЗВИТИИ БАНКОВСКИХ УСЛУГ.....	158
Мамутова Айгуль Калмурзаевна	
QUYOSH NOVUZLARIDA SODIR BO'LUVCHI ISSIQLIK JARAYONLARINING BIR O'LCHAMLI MATEMATIK MODEL.....	165
M.M. Maxmudova, J.J. Kamolov	
ФАКТОРЫ, СДЕРЖИВАЮЩИЕ РАЗВИТИЕ БАНКОВСКОГО ОБСЛУЖИВАНИЯ ВНЕШНЕЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ.....	172
Алиев Али Комил угли, Каримова А.	
ISTE'MOL KREDITLARINING ANAMIYATI VA O'ZIGA XOS JIHATLARI.....	176
S. Qayumov, M. Qurbonov, A. S. Abduraxmanov	
AVTOTRANSPORT XIZMATLARI SAMARADORLIK DARAJASINI OMILLI TAHLILI.....	179
Raximov Azamat Hamroqulovich	
MINTAQA IQTISODIYOTINI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISHDA FIRMALARNING TASHQI BOZORLARGA INTEGRATSIYALASHUV JARAYONLARI: XORIY TAJRIBASI.....	183
Ozodova Farida Zarif qizi	
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ЗОЛОВОАЛЮТНЫМИ РЕЗЕРВАМИ И ВНЕШНИМ ДОЛГОМ КАК ФАКТОР ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ УЧАСТНИКОВ ФИНАНСОВОГО РЫНКА В УСЛОВИЯХ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ.....	187
Зайналов Жахонгир Расулович, Алиева Сусанна Сейрановна	
GENERATIV AI ASOSIDAGI ALGORITMIK NARX BELGILASH MEKANIZMLARI: RAQOBAT IQTISODIYOTIDA MONOPOLLASHUV XAVFI, VANO BO'YICHA SOZLASHUV MUAMMOLARI VA ANTIMONOPOL TARTIBGA SOLISH.....	192
Kendjayeva Dildora Xudayberganovna, Abdumannopova Shirin Olamgir qizi	
РАЗВИТИЕ ЗЕЛЁНОЙ ЭНЕРГЕТИКИ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН КАК ФАКТОР УСТОЙЧИВОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА.....	200
Тураева А. И.	
THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN KNOWLEDGE DELIVERY MODELS.....	204
Daminova Barno Esanovna, Pardayeva Sevinch Sherzod qizi, Inoqov Jasur Komil o'g'li	

THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN KNOWLEDGE DELIVERY MODELS

Daminova Barno Esanovna

Associate Professor, Department of Algorithms and Programming Technologies, Karshi State University

E-mail: barnod@mail.ru

ORCID: 0009-0001-4211-6082

Pardayeva Sevinch Sherzod qizi

Student of Karshi State University

E-mail: sevinchpardayeva1906@gmail.com

Inoqov Jasur Komil o'g'li

Student of Karshi State University

E-mail: jasurinoqov756@gmail.com

Abstract. The role of artificial intelligence technologies in knowledge representation models, their structural characteristics, and applications in modern information systems are examined. The key features of frame-based, semantic network, logical, and production knowledge representation models are analyzed, and decision-making processes in artificial intelligence systems based on these models are discussed. In addition, knowledge-processing methods employed in expert systems, machine learning, and neural networks are explored. The findings highlight the significance of knowledge representation technologies in enhancing the efficiency of artificial intelligence systems and improving the organization of knowledge bases.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, knowledge representation, expert systems, semantic networks, frame model, production model, logical model, neural networks, machine learning.

Annotatsiya. Bilimlarni taqdim etish modellarida sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining o'rni, ularning tarkibiy xususiyatlari hamda zamonaviy axborot tizimlaridagi qo'llanilishi yoritilgan. Bilimlarni ifodalashning freymli, semantik tarmoqli, mantiqiy va produktsion modellarining asosiy jihatlari tahlil qilinib, ular asosida sun'iy intellekt tizimlarida qaror qabul qilish jarayonlari ko'rib chiqilgan. Shuningdek, ekspert tizimlari, mashinaviy o'qitish va neyron tarmoqlarda bilimlarni qayta ishlash usullari tahlil etilgan. Olingan natijalar bilimlarni taqdim etish texnologiyalarining sun'iy intellekt tizimlari samaradorligini oshirish va bilimlar bazalarini takomillashtirishdagi muhim ahamiyatini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: sun'iy intellekt, bilimlarni taqdim etish, ekspert tizimlari, semantik tarmoqlar, freym modeli, produktsion model, mantiqiy model, neyron tarmoqlar, mashinaviy o'qitish.

Аннотация. Рассмотрены роль технологий искусственного интеллекта в моделях представления знаний, их структурные особенности и применение в современных информационных системах. Проанализированы ключевые характеристики фреймовых, семантических, логических и продукционных моделей представления знаний, а также исследованы процессы принятия решений в системах искусственного интеллекта на их основе. Кроме того, изучены методы обработки знаний, используемые в экспертных системах, машинном обучении и нейронных сетях. Полученные результаты подтверждают важность технологий представления знаний для повышения эффективности систем искусственного интеллекта и совершенствования баз знаний.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, представление знаний, экспертные системы, семантические сети, фреймовая модель, продукционная модель, логическая модель, нейронные сети, машинное обучение.

INTRODUCTION

Modern information technologies are developing rapidly, significantly increasing the demand for artificial intelligence (AI) systems. One of the primary tasks of artificial intelligence is to store, process, and efficiently utilize knowledge that reflects human thinking within computer systems. Therefore, knowledge representation models are considered one of the fundamental directions of artificial intelligence.

A knowledge representation model is a method of expressing information and knowledge in a format that can be understood by computer systems. Such models are widely used in expert systems, robotics, automated

control systems, and intelligent information systems. The effectiveness of AI systems largely depends on how knowledge is represented and processed.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Knowledge representation technologies began to develop during the earliest stages of artificial intelligence research. Initially, computer systems were designed only to perform simple calculations; however, the need subsequently arose to create systems capable of making decisions similar to human reasoning. As a result, efficient methods for storing and processing knowledge in computer memory became necessary. During the 1950s–1960s, the first theoretical foundations of artificial intelligence were established. In this period, logical methods of knowledge representation were developed. Based on mathematical logic and algorithmic models, early versions of expert systems were created. Subsequently, semantic networks, frame models, and production models emerged, enabling knowledge to be represented in more convenient and effective forms.

During the 1970s–1980s, with the development of expert systems, the importance of knowledge representation models increased substantially. Expert systems facilitated the solution of complex problems by transferring specialist knowledge into computer systems. During this period, artificial intelligence technologies began to be widely applied in medicine, economics, and technical diagnostics.

Today, knowledge representation technologies are developing in close integration with neural networks, machine learning, and Big Data technologies. Modern AI systems are capable not only of processing existing knowledge but also of generating new knowledge independently. These technologies offer significant advantages, including the easy incorporation of new information and advanced logical analysis capabilities. At the same time, certain limitations remain. For example, semantic networks may become highly complex when processing large volumes of knowledge, while logical inference processes may require considerable computational time.

Knowledge representation is one of the most important areas of artificial intelligence. Through this process, human knowledge, experience, rules, and logical relationships are expressed in a form understandable to computer systems. The effectiveness of AI systems largely depends on the quality of knowledge representation. Therefore, the development and improvement of knowledge representation models remain among the key tasks of AI technologies. Knowledge representation involves not only storing information but also processing, analyzing, generalizing, and generating new knowledge. Modern AI systems are increasingly capable of drawing human-like conclusions by processing large volumes of data. Such systems are widely used in expert systems, virtual assistants, robotics, automated control systems, and medicine.

The primary goal of knowledge representation models is to describe objects, events, and relationships from the real world within computer systems. This enables systems to analyze situations, solve problems, and support decision-making processes. The main requirements for knowledge representation include accuracy, logical consistency, systematic storage, the ability to incorporate new knowledge, and efficient processing.

In AI systems, the knowledge base plays a crucial role. It stores various rules, formulas, objects, and the relationships among them. The inference mechanism utilizes this knowledge to generate logical conclusions. Today, several knowledge representation models are widely used, including logical models, semantic network models, frame models, production models, and neural network models. Each model possesses its own strengths and application areas. For example, logical models provide a high level of precision, whereas semantic networks effectively visualize relationships among knowledge elements.

Knowledge representation technologies are also widely applied in education. E-learning platforms, intelligent testing systems, and virtual laboratories operate on the basis of artificial intelligence technologies. These systems are important for assessing students' knowledge levels and providing personalized learning opportunities. Furthermore, AI technologies assist in medical diagnosis, clinical decision-making, and treatment recommendations. In the banking sector, AI is utilized for financial risk assessment and automated decision-making.

Overall, knowledge representation models constitute one of the key components of artificial intelligence systems and significantly contribute to the effectiveness of modern intelligent technologies. In the future, these technologies are expected to continue evolving and become increasingly integrated into various spheres of human activity.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is based on the analysis of scientific literature, academic articles, monographs, and electronic information resources related to artificial intelligence and knowledge representation models. Data were

collected through a comprehensive review of theoretical and empirical sources. Comparative, systematic, and analytical approaches were applied to examine the characteristics of frame-based, semantic network, logical, and production models. The collected information was processed using content analysis, comparative analysis, and synthesis methods to identify the main features, advantages, and application areas of knowledge representation models in artificial intelligence systems.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The primary purpose of knowledge representation models is to transform human knowledge into a form that computer systems can understand and process. The effectiveness of AI systems largely depends on how knowledge is represented. Therefore, a variety of knowledge representation models have been developed within modern AI technologies. Each model is designed for specific tasks and possesses particular advantages. The most widely used models include logical models, semantic network models, frame models, production models, and neural network models.

The logical model is based on the principles of mathematical logic and represents knowledge through formulas and logical expressions. It enables systems to perform logical reasoning and support decision-making processes.

For example: If $A \rightarrow B$ and A is true, then B is also true.

The advantages of logical models include accuracy, logical consistency, and strong inference capabilities. However, managing a large number of logical formulas may become challenging in complex systems.

Semantic networks represent knowledge in graphical form. Objects are represented by nodes, while relationships among them are represented by edges.

For example: "Student" \rightarrow "Studies at a university".

This model is widely used in natural language processing and expert systems. Its advantages include visual representation of knowledge, clear relationships, and the ease of incorporating new information. Nevertheless, the model may become more complex as the size of the system increases.

The frame model represents objects and events in a structured format. Each frame contains information about a specific object.

Frame: Student; name, faculty, year, group.

This model is highly effective in expert systems and virtual assistants because it supports structured knowledge storage.

The production model operates on the basis of "IF-THEN" rules and is widely applied in automated control systems and expert systems.

For example: IF temperature is high, THEN the cooling system turns on.

Its advantages include simplicity, rapid decision-making, and the ease of adding new rules.

Neural networks function in a manner similar to the human brain. They learn from large datasets and generate conclusions based on acquired experience. Neural networks are widely used in face recognition, speech recognition, machine translation, and medical diagnostics. Today, they represent one of the most significant directions in AI development.

Machine learning is one of the key areas of artificial intelligence. It enables computer systems to learn from experience and improve their performance over time. The primary objective is to extract useful knowledge from large datasets using statistical and mathematical methods. For example, platforms such as YouTube and Instagram analyze user preferences and provide personalized recommendations through machine learning algorithms.

Big Data plays a significant role in the advancement of artificial intelligence. Today, enormous volumes of data are generated through the Internet, and traditional methods are often insufficient for processing them efficiently. AI technologies are therefore employed to analyze, classify, and predict patterns within such data. The integration of Big Data and AI is widely applied in economic forecasting, climate analysis, marketing, and security systems.

In the future, artificial intelligence technologies are expected to form the foundation of smart robots, smart cities, digital education systems, and automated transportation. Their continued development is anticipated to enhance economic efficiency, reduce routine workloads, and facilitate the automation of complex processes.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Knowledge representation models constitute one of the core components of artificial intelligence systems. They enhance the efficiency of knowledge storage, processing, and utilization. Models such as semantic

networks, frame systems, logical systems, and production systems play a significant role in the development of artificial intelligence. As AI technologies continue to evolve, knowledge representation methods are also expected to advance, contributing to the creation of more sophisticated, efficient, and intelligent information systems.

References

1. Daminova B. E. et al. SUN'IIY INTELLEKT VA KIBERXAVFSIZLIK // *Экономика и социум*. – 2025. – № 5-1 (132). – С. 212–215.
2. Daminova B. E. et al. SUN'IIY NEYRON TARMOQLARINING NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA AMALIY ILOVALARIDA ISHLASH USULLARI // *Экономика и социум*. – 2025. – № 5-1 (132). – С. 226–230.
3. Daminova B. E. et al. ROBOTOTEXNIKA VA AVTOMATLASHTIRISHNING AHAMIYATI // *Экономика и социум*. – 2025. – № 5-1 (132). – С. 208–211.
4. Daminova B. E., Omonov J. M., Norqo'chqorov Y. Y. NUTQNI TANISH TIZIMINI CHUQUR NEYRON TARMOQLARI YORDAMIDA YARATISH BOSQICHLARI // *Экономика и социум*. – 2025. – № 4-2 (131). – С. 221–227.
5. Daminova B. E. et al. ELEKTRON HUKUMAT VA ELEKTRON RAQAMLI IMZONING QO'LLANILISHI // *Экономика и социум*. – 2025. – № 4-2 (131). – С. 216–220.
6. Daminova B. E. et al. SUN'IIY INTELLEKT SOHASIDA QO'LLANADIGAN ZAMONAVIIY PYTHON KUTUBXONALARI // *Экономика и социум*. – 2025. – № 4-2 (131). – С. 205–209.
7. Daminova B. E. et al. ARDUINO PLATFORMASIDAN FOYDALANIB SUV SARFINI HISOBLOVCHI DASTURIY VA TEXNIK TA'MINOT ISHLAB CHIQISH // *Экономика и социум*. – 2025. – № 4-2 (131). – С. 210–215.
8. Alimovna E. Y., Alimovna E. G., Burievna M. S. Historical Stages of Innovative Processes in Higher Education of Uzbekistan // *Solid State Technology*. – 2020. – Vol. 63. – No. 6. – P. 9824–9834.
9. Alimovna E. G. The Role of Context in the Interpretation of Prepositional Phrases in Predicative Constructions // *Central Asian Journal of Academic Research*. – 2025. – Vol. 3. – No. 9. – P. 103–106.
10. Alimovna E. Y., Alimovna E. G. Policy of "Cultural Revolution" in Uzbekistan and Methods of Its Implementation // *International Journal on Economics, Finance and Sustainable Development*. – 2020. – Vol. 2. – No. 11. – P. 4–6.
11. Alimovna E. G. Study of the Semantic and Syntactical Analyses of Prepositional Constructions // *PARTICULAR PAGE NO.* – 2022.
12. Jabborovich J. K., Keldiyorovna O. M. Syntactical Methods of Uzbek and English Language Terminology // *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*. – 2020. – Vol. 24. – No. 6. – P. 3117–3122.
13. Omonova M. Nominative-Definitive Functions of Components of Ameliorative Terms in English and Uzbek Languages // *Theoretical & Applied Science*. – 2021. – No. 4. – P. 84–86.
14. Omonova M. K. Comparative Analysis of Semantical Features of Meliorative Terms in English and Uzbek // *Experientia Est Optima Magistra*. – 2021. – P. 269–272.
15. Omonova M. Innovative Ways of Teaching Vocabulary in ESL and EFL Classrooms // *Science and Education*. – 2020. – Vol. 1. – No. 7. – P. 229–233.
16. Журакулова Н. Х., Ихтиярова Г. А. СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕТОДИКИ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ ПО ТЕМЕ «НУКЛЕИНОВЫЕ КИСЛОТЫ» ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫМИ СРЕДСТВАМИ // *SCIENCE AND WORLD*. – 2013. – С. 30.
17. Jurakulova N. K. Opportunities of E-Learning Environment to Improve the Quality of Education // *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*. – 2019. – Vol. 7. – No. 12.
18. Rizayeva B., Daminova B. STATISTIK TAHLILDA DASTURIY VOSITALARDAN FOYDALANISH // *MUHANDISLIK VA IQTISODIYOT*. – 2026. – Т. 4.
19. Daminova B. Organizational and Economic Mechanisms and Conceptual Directions of Tourism Development in the Region // *Green Economy and Development*. – 2024. – Vol. 3. – No. 7.
20. Esanovna D. B. Organizational and Economic Mechanisms and Conceptual Directions of Tourism Development in the Region // *International Journal of Social Science & Interdisciplinary Research*. – 2025. – Vol. 14. – No. 11. – P. 91–94.

muhandislik

& iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir Alibekov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Abdurahmon Qurbonov

2026. № 6

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali 26.06.2023-yildan
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan
№S-5669245 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: №095310.

**Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahri Yunusobod
tumani 15-mavze 19-uy**

+998 93 718 40 07

<https://muhandislik-iqtisodiyot.uz/index.php/journal>

t.me/yait_2100